

Online Attendance System with Geolocation Tagging Feature based on Progressive Web Apps (PWA) on CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri

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Abstract:

Currently the development of technology is so fast, and penetrated into various sectors. The development of this technology in order to complete various kinds of work efficiently, quickly, and accurately in an organization. Especially the attendance system, attendance is an important thing in the company, especially to see the level of employee discipline in work attendance. In manual attendance, we find that there are various kinds of errors in data processing, allowing fraud in attendance and the resulting data is inaccurate and tends to be slow. So that an online attendance system is made using Progressive Web Apps so that employees can easily attend attendance via their respective smartphone according to the employee's work location, because the system already uses the Geolocation Tagging feature. The attendance system also includes external services, monthly attendance recap, application for permits, illness, and leave. This system was developed by programming the PHP Framework Laravel with a MySQL database and using Progressive Web Apps (PWA) so that it is mobile friendly and can be uploaded on the Playstore (Android).

Keywords — *Geolocation Tagging, Attendance, Progressive Web Apps*

and accurately.[1] Attendance system is a very important thing in a company in order to see the level of discipline of employees at work.[2] Attendance is a document that records the attendance of every employee in the company. [3]

CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri is a private company, one of the retailers from Shell Indonesia, currently CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri has several locations so it requires an attendance system that can be accessed from various locations.

The system that is currently running is still using manual attendance so that it is possible for errors to occur in data processing, fraud occurs, and the resulting inaccurate data tends to be slow. The attendance process carried out by each branch will record in the

Personal Extreme Programming Method at CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri Serpong South Tangerang [4], designing an attendance application as well, but there are several weaknesses, namely the appearance of the application is not user friendly, the desktop display and the display is not like the appearance of the mobile application, besides that the application is not designed for several branches, and also attendance does not use location coordinates according to the location of the employee working.

Based on the problems that occur above in attendance management, the author will create an attendance system that can be carried out in each branch using employee smartphones because this system is based on Progressive Web Apps (PWA)

which is already user friendly. By doing Geolocation Tagging on the system in each branch, employees are required to access the attendance system according to the location points registered in the system, if the employee's attendance is above 100 meters from the location registered the employee cannot take attendance, In addition, other features employees can apply for a permit, illness, external service, or leave on the system and can monitor the level of discipline of each employee himself.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research process is carried out by identifying the problems that occur in CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri, in the identification process carried out by direct observation to the location, and conducting various discussions and interviews regarding the flow of attendance.

After that, the author designed the flow design of the attendance system, designed the interface, then carried out the coding process, and testing. Then after the live attendance system, an experiment was carried out for 1 week to see the performance of the attendance system, and accommodate some input and suggestions from employees who use the attendance application so that the author can make improvements if there are some problems at the location such as errors and others.

Here the author makes a system based on Progressive Web Apps (PWA), which is a web-based application that contains like a web page but has various functions such as notifications, add to homescreen, and applications can work offline, besides that PWA can also be uploaded to the Android Playstore. so it's like a Native Android application [5]. Here are some characteristics of PWA-based systems [6]:

- 1) Progressive – compatible for all browsers and devices.
- 2) Responsive – can adapt to any type of screen.
- 3) Connectivity Independent – can run when offline or the network is unstable.
- 4) App Like – Web App is like Native App.
- 5) Fresh – always provides the latest data.
- 6) Safe – use an encrypted connection (HTTPS).
- 7) Discoverable – easy to find on search engines.
- 8) Re-engageable – easy to open Web App via notification.

- 9) Installable – can be installed to mobile devices.
- 10) Linkable – easy to share web app via link.

In addition, this system also uses the Geolocation Tagging feature to register each branch, Geolocation Tagging is the process of adding geospatial information to various media. Media that has undergone the Geolocation Tagging process will have coordinate information, the coordinates contain longitude, and latitude. This can later be positioned correctly on the map. [7]. Geotagging can also help find various kinds of location-specific information.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here are the results of the design and attendance system on CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri:

3.1 Business process

The problem identification process has been carried out and the following is an overview of the author's analysis for the employee attendance system for various branches of the company.

Fig.1. Analysis of the absence of entry and exit

3.2 Design

After the problem identification process is carried out, from the results obtained the need for the application, then a system model is made, where the design is designed with a user case diagram.

Fig.2. System Diagram Usecase Overview

3.3 Coding

After the design process is carried out, the author performs the coding process, using the PHP programming language with the Laravel framework and using the MySQL database. Here there are 2 views of the application, namely the Admin Backend view and the Frontend (Mobile) view.

3.4 Results

After the coding process is carried out, the following are the results of the application that the author made after the testing process was carried out:

Fig.3. Attendance Application Main View

Fig.4. Display of Absent Sign-In Employees

Fig.5. Weekly Attendance Recap Display

Fig.7. Monthly Attendance Recap Display

Fig.6. Display of Sick, Permission, and Leave Applications

Fig8. Display of Absent Employees going home

Fig.9. Admin Display Absent Monitoring

Fig.10. Admin Display Approve Submission

Fig.11. Admin Display Attendance Summary

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After designing and implementing the attendance application at CV Trivia Oktana Mandiri. Here are some details of the conclusion:

1. The application helps make it easier for companies to monitor the attendance of employees from previously still using manual attendance.

2. Attendance can be used in various branches in the company, because there are coordinates for the location of the branch, so employees are required to be absent at the nearest branch location according to the employee's homebase
3. Applications based on Progressive Web Apps so that the application can be used on each employee's smartphone like a native mobile application
4. Employees can view attendance recap, apply for illness, permission, leave, and admin can monitor the level of discipline of each employee.

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